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An Assessment of Impact of Motivation on Academic Staff Job Performance of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

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***Abstract:** This paper assessed the impact of motivation on academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper is a position paper that depends on secondary data to gather its data. The secondary data were collected from both print and online publications. The paper revealed that motivation is very vital to the realization of tertiary institutions goals. The paper pointed out that motivation has great impact on the academic staff job performance in the tertiary institutions. Based on the finding, the paper recommends that increment in the funding of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The tertiary institutions should ensure; prompt payment of salary and allowances, regular promotion, provision of instructional materials, infrastructure facilities, provision of conducive environment, training, commendation, praise and award and involvement of academic staff decision making.*

***Key words:** Academic staff job performance, Motivation, Tertiary Education.*

Introduction

Tertiary education is an education that is anchored on teaching, research and provision of community services for the total transformation of the nation (Ogunode, & Akuh, 2024). Tertiary education is an educational system designed to solve local, national and international pressing problems (Ogunode & Musa 2024). Tertiary education can be defined as the planned and organized system of learning designed for the total development of individuals and the total transformation of the society through the utilization of teaching, research and provision of community service (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie

2023). Tertiary education fosters individual development and growth as well as impacts positively on the society at large (Schrader-King, 2024).

Tertiary education, also known as higher education, refers to educational programs offered by universities, colleges, and other institutions beyond secondary education. It encompasses undergraduate and postgraduate studies, providing students with advanced knowledge, skills, and qualifications in their chosen field of study ((Proctoredu 2023).The goals of tertiary education according to the FGN National Policy on Education (2013), shall be to: contribute to national development through high level manpower training; provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interests of all Nigerians; provide high quality career counseling and lifelong learning program that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for self-reliance and the world of work; reduce skill shortages through the production of skilled manpower relevant to the needs of the labor market; promote and encourage scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and promote national and international understanding and interaction.

The realization of the goals and objectives of tertiary institutions depends on the academic staff. Academic staff as the name implies are professional that handles the teaching, research programme of the higher institutions and also perform other academic services. The role of academic staff in the development of higher institutions cannot be underestimated because the academic staff are the implementer of the instruction in the educational institutions (Ogunode, Jegede & Abubakar, 2020). Ogunode and Adamu (2021) defined Academic staff as the teaching staff in the higher institutions. Academic staff are the implementer of the school curriculum and lecture presenter. Academic staff are the teachers and deliver of instruction in the higher institutions. Ogunode, et al (2020) noted that Academic staff are professional personnel in charge of teaching or lecturing in the higher institutions. The Academic staff members are the teaching staff of the tertiary institutions. They are called lecturers. They are involved in three major functions in the institutions which are teaching and researching and community services. The academic staff are categorized into Graduate Assistant, Assistant Lecturer, Lecturer II, Lecturer I, senior Lecturer, Associate professor/Reader and Professors. Academic staff are critical factors in the higher education goals attainment.

The job performance of academic staff in Nigerian tertiary institutions appear to be low due to many factors such as poor motivation. Academic staff are poorly motivated (Egu, Ogbonna, Obike, & Obiuto, 2014). Kamoh, Ughili, & Abada, (2013) identified conditions responsible for low teacher morale and the difficulty in attracting and retaining quality personnel into the teaching profession. Teachers, out of desperation have decided to make the profession more lucrative by introducing all forms of fraudulent tendencies. The lecturers in a bid to leave an exuberant and flamboyant lifestyle on campus go the extra mile of recruiting students in their classes who serve as middlemen between them and the students, the middlemen move around after every examination to inform their course mate that sorting of a particular course is in progress, the interested members will then give their registration number and the specified amount for the grade they want” the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) embarked on an indefinite strike over unresolved and contentious issues with the Federal Government” (Vanguard newspaper 29th August 2017). It is based on this, that this study seeks to assess the impact on motivation on academic staff job performance in the Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Purpose of the study

1. The objective of this study is to assess the impact of motivation on academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Research Question

1. What is the impact of motivation on academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria?

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory. This is equally called, the motivation-hygiene theory. This is because; the five different levels identified by Maslow were collapsed into only two levels: Motivators and hygiene factors. According to Herzberg (1968) cited in Ajayi and Ayodele (2002), the factors that were mentioned as leading to job satisfaction (satisfiers) were found to be unrelated to those resulting in job dissatisfaction (dissatisfiers).

(A) Motivator or Satisfiers: These include responsibility, achievement, work itself, recognition and advancement. There are roughly equivalent to Maslow's higher-level needs.

(B) Hygiene Factor or Dissatisfiers: These are things that will not simply motivate the workers, but from time to time, serve as dissatisfiers when they are not present. This hygiene factor is a none-motivator of workers.

Working conditions are related to this theory because, the absence of none-motivator brings a very high negative feelings and their presence generally bring workers satisfaction. These include, working conditions, salary, company policy, technical supervision, interpersonal relations, status and security. These are preventive and environmental in nature. They prevent dissatisfaction and are roughly equivalent to Maslow's lower level needs (Alonge, Onnoh,, Olusesean, Ojo, & Nathaniel, 2020).

Review of Related Literatures

Concept of Academic staff job performance

Academic staff job performance is the total performance of teaching, researching and community services responsibilities an academic staff has carried out and still carrying out in the institutions where he or she work at a particular time. Academic staff job performance is the general record of tasks carried out by an academic staff to be compare to the assigned responsibilities and functions given to them. Academic staff job performance can also be seen as the measuring of a specific and general tasks given to faculty in an institutions and they are expected to carry them out within a specific timeline (Ogunode, & Ibrahim, 2023). Ziegler (2005) viewed academic performance with particularly effective action by a teaching staff which is consistently observed as a superior achievement in an education setting.

According to Andy, Emmanuel & Obabuike (2020), academic performance is a tool to helping the society in offering solution to problem with a view to enhancing societal well-being. In this research, academic staff performance is measured with productivity. Ogunode, ThankGod and Olatunde-Aiyedun (2022) stated that the academic staff job performance constitutes all activities and functions it is expected of an academic to execute within a specific time. It has to do with the abilities of the academic to fulfill his/her duties in the institutions. Academic staff job performance means an assigned responsibilities and functions given to an academic staff to actualize the aims and objectives of the institutions and the decree execution or accomplishment.

Concept of Motivation

Motivation as the forces that influence an individual to give his or her best in an institution and realization of goals. Motivation is the drive that influences an individual to achieve the maximum output for himself or an institution. Motivation is an invisible drive that influences the action of an

individual towards a particular goal (Josiah, Audu, and Ogunode (2023). Motivation can be viewed as a force that propels an individual to carry out some tasks or production (Ogunode, Salman, & Ayoko, 2023). Motivation is a concept that has many benefits both to the organization and individual employees, motivation helps to develop an organization's human resources and draw individuals to join the organization and remain in it, it also increases the level of efficiency of the employees and builds friendly relationships among them which in turn leads to organizational goals achievement (Abubakar, Soba & Yusuf, 2022).

Motivation as “the factor that induces an individual to behave in a purposive manner to achieve his or her personal or organizational goals” (Badu (2005). Motivation as “a process in which people choose between alternative forms of behaviour to achieve personal goals” (Cole (002). Motivation as the process of influencing or stimulating a person to take action that will accomplish desired goals (Peretomode 2005).

Impact of Motivation on Academic staff job performance in tertiary Institutions

Motivation is very important to the realization of tertiary institutions goals and objectives (). Motivation of academic staff in the universities led to improved job performance according to (Ogunode, & Ibrahim, 2023) Omale, Ojo, Ibrahim, & Yusuf, (2023) did a study with a main goal of determining the elements that influence academic staff members in Nigerian universities' levels of enthusiasm and productivity and they found out unfavorable correlation between academic staff performance and lucid desire. Also, Abubakar, Soba & Yusuf (2022) carried out a study that examined the impact of salary and promotion on the performance of academic staff of Bauchi state University Gadau (BASUG) with high productivity as the moderator variable and they discovered that there is positive and significant relationship between salary, promotion, job satisfaction and high productivity on the performance of academic staff of the University.

Yahaya, Jamari, Mustapha, Abubakar & Inuwa (2019) carried out a study that examined factors motivating academic staff with a focus on Gombe State University by assessing motivational level and identifying factors of motivation, as well as measuring the strength of the motivating techniques of academic staff used in the University and the study showed that the available motivational tools in the University and strength of the techniques of motivating academic staff of Gombe State University is moderately fair. “By motivational communication, by making employees feel better at work, by appreciating ‘the power of inclusion’ and by sharing a vision with employees would not only create a productive employee and a pleasant transaction but also would generate self-confidence, self-discipline, cooperation, improve efficiency and strengthen bonds in the long run” (Biswas and Giri (2017).

Moreover, Osakwe (2014) did a study that determined the factors affecting motivation and job satisfaction of non-management academic staff of universities in South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria and the study disclosed that there is no significant difference between male and female non-management academic staff motivation and job satisfaction. It was also found that highly motivated non-management academic staffs perform their job better than poorly motivated staff. It was recommended that university authorities and the government should pay increasing attention to the motivation of non-management academic staff in order to boost their job performance and satisfaction thereby enhancing high productivity.

Academic staff job satisfaction has significant relationship with their job performance and the academic performance of their students. Attitudes of academic staff are effected, in part, by workplace conditions such as a positive and safe environment, a supportive administration, career progression,

commensurate salary, supportive work team, and the appeal of the job itself. It is also connected with their autonomy. Autonomy in the true sense, should be the privilege of the university system so as to enable it operate with full vigor for the fulfillment of goals and objectives. Academic autonomy, in relation to offering courses, evolving evaluation methods, teaching, research and extension activities is available. Financial autonomy is vital for continuation of universities as centers for excellence and the need, at present, is to initiate steps for fund generation and reduction of its dependence on the government to the extent possible, thus paving the way for self-reliance (Noordin and Muindi in Osakwe 2014).

Findings

The paper discovered that motivation is very vital to the realization of tertiary institutions goals. The paper pointed out that motivation has great impact on the academic staff job performance in the tertiary institutions.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper assessed the impact of motivation on academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper revealed that motivation is very vital to the realization of tertiary institutions goals. The paper pointed out that motivation has great impact on the academic staff job performance in the tertiary institutions.

Based on the finding, the paper recommends that increment in the funding of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The tertiary institutions should ensure; prompt payment of salary and allowances, regular promotion, provision of instructional materials, infrastructure facilities, provision of conducive environment, training, commendation, praise and award and involvement of academic staff decision making.

References

1. Abubakar, S., Soba, N.H & Yusuf, Y.A. (2022). Impacts of motivation on academic staff performance in Nigerian Universities: A study of Bauchi State University Gadau. *International Journal of Intellectual Discourse (IJID)*, 5(2), 27-34
2. Ajayi, I. A., & Ayodele, J. B. (2002). *Fundamentals of Educational Management*. Lagos, a. Nigeria: Dolphin Publishers.
3. Alonge, B., D, Onnoh, O., G, Olusesean, O, J., Ojo, O, A. & Nathaniel, O, O. (2020). Working Conditions and Salary as Correlates of Teachers' Productivity in Government-Owned a. Secondary Schools in Emure Local Government Area of Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Issues*, 6(1),90-97
4. Badu, E. E. (2005). Employee Motivation in University Libraries in Ghana: A Comparative a. Analysis. *Information development*, 21(1), 38-46.
5. Biswas, W. & Giri, A. (2017). Effectiveness of motivational management on employee performance in higher educational institutions of West Bengal. *International Journal for Research in Engineering Application & Management*, 3(9), 2454-9150.
6. Cole G.A. (2002). *Personnel and Human Resource Management*. C&C Offset China.
7. Egu, H.N., Ogbonna, E. N. Obike, N. C. & Obiuto, C. C. (2014). Managing stress among lecturers in polytechnics of South Eastern, Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(6)333-338.

8. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National policy on education. 4th ed. Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
9. Josiah, H. F., Audu, B. C., and Ogunode, N. J. (2023). Motivational strategies and teachers' job performance in post-basic education and career development (PBECD), Nigeria. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 6 (7), 22-31.
10. Kamoh, N. M., Ughili, L. S., & Abada, A. A. (2013). Enhancing the Teacher Profession: key to Revamping the Education Sector in Nigeria. *Academic Research International*, 4(1), 129.
11. Noordin, F., & Jusoff, K. (2009). Levels of job satisfaction amongst Malaysian academic staff. *Asian Social Science*, 5(5), 122-128.
12. Ogunode N., J & Eimuhi, J. O (2023). Academic Staff Job Performance in Tertiary Institutions. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 1-16
13. Ogunode, N., J. Kasimu, S. & Ibrahim, I. (2023). Motivation and Academic Staff of Nigerian Universities. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 02(07) 185-198
14. Ogunode, N., J, Salman, A., A. & Ayoko, V., O (2023). Motivation, Non-Academic Staff' Job Performance and Tertiary Education in Nigeria. *Electronic Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 5(III),20-32
15. Ogunode, N, J. & Ibrahim, G., F (2023). Impact of motivation on academic staff job performance in tertiary institutions in nigeria. *Analytical Journal of Education and Development*, 3(11), 335-345
16. Ogunode, N.J., Jegede & Musa, A. (2021). Problems facing academic staff of Nigerian universities and the way forward. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4, 230-239.
17. Ogunode, N. J. & Adamu, D. G. (2021). Shortage of academic staff in the higher institution of learning in Nigeria. *Central Asian Journal of Social Sciences and History*, 2(3), 109-123.
18. Ogunode, N,J & Akuh, E, A (2024). Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) and Staff Training in Tertiary Education in Nigeria. *American Journal of Open University Education*, 1, (7),48-54
19. Ogunode, N.J. & Musa, L. (2024). Entrepreneurial Education Programme in Tertiary Education in Nigeria.
20. Ogunode N.J., Edinoh, K., & Okolie, R.C. (2023). Public Private Partnership Model and Implementation of
 - a. Tertiary Education Program in Nigeria. *AMERICAN Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development*, 01(06), 1-12.
21. Osakwe, R. N (2014). Factors affecting motivation and job satisfaction of academic staff of universities in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. *International Education Studies*. 7(7), 43-50.
22. Peretomode, V.F. (2005). *Educational administration, applied concepts and theoretical perspectives for students and practitioners*. Lagos: Joja Publishers.
23. Proctoredu (2023) Tertiary Education - Definition & Meaning
<https://proctoredu.com/glossary/tertiary-education>

24. Schrader-King, K. (2024). Tertiary Education
<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/tertiaryeducation>
25. Victor, A.A. & Babatunde, E.G. (2014). Motivation and effective performance of academic staff in Higher Education (Case Study of *Adekunle Ajasin University, Ondo State, Nigeria*). *Online Submission*, 1(2), 157-163.
26. Yahaya, M.A., Jamari, A.A., Mustapha, B, Abubakar, A. & Inuwa, M.M. (2019). Factors motivating academic staff: a case study of Gombe State University, Nigeria. *Qualitative and Quantitative Research Review*, 4(3), 113-139.
27. Ziegler, A. (2005). *The actiope model of giftness*. Cambridge, U.K: Cambridge University Press.